

Explaining stated preferences for nature-based solutions for climate adaptation: A systematic mapping review of empirical evidence[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Nature-based solutions (NbS) are increasingly implemented to support climate adaptation and reduce natural hazard risks. Public preferences for NbS are frequently assessed through stated preference methods, such as contingent valuation and discrete choice experiments, which elicit willingness-to-pay (WTP). However, the individual determinants shaping these preferences remain insufficiently understood. This review synthesises evidence from 90 peer-reviewed studies to examine which explanatory variables have been used to account for stated preferences for NbS and how these have been conceptualised and measured. Particular attention is given to the prevalence and predictive power of social–psychological variables, the extent of theoretical grounding in variable selection, and the operationalisation of these constructs.

The findings show that both sociodemographic and social–psychological factors influence WTP. Higher income, education, and, in many cases, lower age are positively associated with WTP, while risk perception, hazard experience, environmental attitudes, and knowledge emerge as the most frequent social–psychological predictors. At the same time, the review identifies a lack of theoretical foundation, widespread reliance on ad hoc variable selection, and limited use of validated instruments, which together restrict comparability and hinder cumulative knowledge building. Addressing these shortcomings is crucial to advance empirical research and to better align NbS implementation with citizens' values and priorities, thereby supporting more inclusive and effective climate adaptation strategies.

1. Introduction

Human-induced climate change is one of the most pressing global challenges of the 21st century, necessitating adaptation to protect vulnerable ecosystems and communities from inevitable impacts, such as floods and heat stress [1]. A vast body of research assesses different adaptation measures, their effectiveness, and the barriers and facilitating factors for their implementation and acceptance [2–6]. While traditional, “grey” infrastructure, such as flood barriers or air conditioning systems, remains a dominant strategy, a growing body of research suggests that Nature-based Solutions (NbS) may offer cost-effective and more sustainable climate adaptation measures. NbS are defined as “Actions to protect, sustainably manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems that address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits” [7, p. 1], ranging from protective or restorative measures such as the restoration of forests or wetlands to newly implemented structures including urban green roofs [8]. Compared to grey solutions,

NbS are potentially less costly and offer substantial co-benefits for biodiversity and human well-being [9]. Despite these benefits, the widespread adoption of NbS faces several obstacles. Benefits are difficult to monetise and therefore frequently underrepresented in decision making, and long-term economic gains tend to be underestimated compared to grey solutions, contributing to a lack of financing for NbS [8]. Research further indicates that NbS are often incorrectly perceived as less effective than grey infrastructure [10–12]. Addressing these obstacles requires a clearer understanding of the social and cultural factors driving public preferences [13], as cooperation and community engagement have been identified as essential to the success of NbS, and public acceptance carries greater significance for NbS than for grey infrastructure [10,14–16].

These challenges necessitate a better understanding of people's valuation of and preferences for NbS, as well as their drivers. This is frequently done through stated preference methods, such as contingent valuation and discrete choice experiments, which elicit monetary values for non-market goods and services whose benefits are not priced

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in markets [17,18]. By making NbS benefits, such as flood protection or urban cooling, economically visible and comparable to the costs of implementation, such methods provide an important evidence base for decisions on NbS investment [8] and allow for the systematic investigation of the drivers of WTP. Stated preference methods are grounded in the principle of utility maximisation, which posits that rational agents select the option yielding the greatest personal benefit, and are operationalised through random utility theory, which further acknowledges that not all factors driving choices can be observed [19,20]. However, utility theory itself provides little guidance on which individual or social factors shape preferences, and a substantial body of evidence has established that WTP for environmental goods varies across sociodemographic groups, with income receiving particular attention [21]. Contributions from behavioural economics and psychology further demonstrate that choices are not purely rational but are also shaped by cognitive biases and heuristics [22,23], as well as social-psychological factors [6,24]. These social-psychological factors, such as values, worldviews, and beliefs, add significant explanatory power in predicting environmental behaviours, intentions, and preferences [25–27], reflecting a broader shift in the literature beyond the assumption of purely rational actors. If certain social groups, their perceptions, or attitudes systematically shape whether and how much they are willing to pay for NbS, this has direct implications for how NbS are communicated, targeted, and financed. This has led to the inclusion of social-psychological explanatory variables alongside sociodemographic ones in stated preference studies, and consequently a growing body of research investigates WTP for NbS incorporating a range of such factors to explain heterogeneity in preferences [28–31].

Across stated preference studies on NbS, the diverse range of constructs investigated to explain preference heterogeneity are rarely conceptualised in the same way [14,32], which may be because utility theory itself provides little guidance on which psychological or social factors to include or how to measure them. Meanwhile, the widespread absence of explicit behavioural or psychological theories appears to contribute to this lack of standardisation in construct selection and variable measurement. This may underlie the limited comparability observed across stated preference studies on NbS, even when conceptually similar variables are examined. This inconsistency also carries practical consequences: benefit transfer, a widely used approach for applying valuation results from primary studies to other contexts, relies on the comparability of study characteristics and explanatory variables, and its validity is hampered when those variables are poorly or inconsistently defined [33,34]. Shared theoretical frameworks may address this by providing a common conceptual vocabulary that structures the selection and operationalisation of constructs, thereby facilitating cross-study comparison and cumulative knowledge development [35]. In a review of the role of theory in adaptation research Kuhllicke et al. [35] find that Protection Motivation Theory [36, PMT] is the most frequently applied, followed by the Theory of Planned Behaviour [37]. A review of PMT studies revealed that its application is often incomplete, with researchers measuring and testing only a subset of its constructs [38], and Kuhllicke et al. [35] further note that theory use varies with the hazard type and scientific field.

To systematically investigate these patterns among stated preference studies on NbS for climate adaptation and hazard mitigation, this paper presents a systematic mapping review with the goal of analysing the explanatory variables and theoretical frameworks used to explain WTP for NbS. Specifically, we focus on theories beyond those that underpin stated preference methods themselves, such as random utility theory, and direct our attention towards the use of psychological or behavioural theories aimed at explaining heterogeneity in preferences. Although the primary objective of stated preference studies is to elicit the non-market value of NbS [17], understanding which factors drive heterogeneity in WTP is important for the social and political acceptance of NbS. Analysing the predictors of WTP moves stated preference research beyond describing who is willing to

pay more towards understanding why, which is relevant for practice. Identifying attitudinal, normative, and sociodemographic drivers of WTP can inform the design of behaviourally grounded environmental policies, guide the targeting of communication campaigns, and expose distributional implications, which is essential for fair decision making [6,17]. Moreover, demonstrating that WTP is shaped by consistent drivers across settings strengthens the credibility and external relevance of stated preference studies [18]. Our review explicitly focuses on studies that quantify preferences monetarily, as this introduces a consistent outcome variable by incorporating budget constraints into preference elicitation in a way that non-monetary scales do not [17, 18]. Previous reviews [10,11] have identified factors influencing NbS acceptance, and existing meta-analyses have aggregated WTP values [28]. However, neither connected explanatory variables to WTP values nor addressed their theoretical grounding and operationalisation. Conceptual mapping of theory use has been conducted in related fields [39,40], but remains underexplored in stated preference studies on NbS. This review addresses that gap by comparing studies with and without a theoretical basis, examining the theoretical derivation, conceptualisation, and measured impact of constructs used to explain monetary valuations of NbS. We discuss the explanatory variables that are most commonly investigated and found to be most often significant, analyse to what extent these variables are grounded in theory, and reflect on underexplored constructs that could enhance the theoretical depth and practical relevance of NbS preference studies. The review thereby aims to provide guidance on which explanatory variables and theories are most relevant for future research and on how more consistent measurement and theoretical grounding could improve both the scientific comparability and the external relevance of stated preference studies on NbS.

2. Theoretical context

This section provides a brief comparison of the theories used by the reviewed studies, providing context for the analyses in the results and discussion sections. In particular, we elaborate on the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), the Protection Motivation Theory (PMT), and the Value-Belief-Norm Theory (VBN), which are commonly used to explain environmental behaviour [41]. For more extensive descriptions of theories, we refer to previous works [39,40].

All three theories focus on the formation of (behavioural) intentions¹ as the primary predictor of actual behaviour and assume reasoned decisions [41]. In TPB, intentions result from a deliberative evaluation of attitudes toward the behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control [42,43]. In PMT, intentions emerge from motivational processes based on two cognitive pathways: threat appraisal and coping appraisal [36]. In contrast, VBN theory considers intentions as normatively driven, arising from personal norms that are activated through the internalisation of values and beliefs about environmental harm and individual responsibility [24].

Although each theory has a distinct theoretical foundation, several conceptual overlaps exist. Both TPB and PMT include self-reflective beliefs about one's competence and control. Perceived behavioural control in TPB closely resembles self-efficacy in PMT's coping appraisal component, with both theories basing their constructs on Bandura [44]'s social cognitive theory of behaviour [44,45], suggesting that individuals who believe they can succeed are more likely to form intentions and carry them out [46,47]. Further, while PMT tends to be applied to specific hazard situations and focuses on protective behaviour, TPB has broader applications and generally addresses wider behaviour, stemming from its origin in health psychology. TPB has been described

¹ While studies applying TPB often use the term “behavioural” intentions, we hereafter use “intention” for conceptual clarity and consistency across theories

as reflecting a deliberative weighing of costs and benefits when forming behavioural intentions [41], whereas PMT similarly incorporates evaluative processes by weighing the threat against one's coping capacity. Both TPB and VBN incorporate normative influences but differ in their framing: TPB's subjective norm reflects perceived social pressure [41], whereas VBN's personal norm represents an internalised moral obligation [24,48]. TPB focuses on intentions to modify behaviour shaped by anticipated outcomes, while VBN reflects stable values and moral principles that guide action [49]. Originally, TPB defines attitude as the evaluation of a specific target behaviour, but in environmental studies, it is often conceptualised as a general attitude towards environmental causes [50]. This is why it is frequently measured via the New Environmental Paradigm (NEP) scale [51], reflecting these more general attitudes. The NEP aligns conceptually and operationally with VBN's ecological worldview, which is similarly shaped by values and is therefore frequently used by studies employing this theory [24,51]. Empirical evidence has also linked values to attitudes within TPB and shown that TPB's predictive power improves when personal norms are included [41], demonstrating the conceptual overlap between these theories. PMT's threat appraisal [36] aligns with the VBN construct of awareness of consequences, referring to an individual's recognition of environmental threat. Furthermore, in VBN, the belief that one's actions can influence these outcomes, reminiscent of coping appraisal in PMT, is expected to activate a personal moral obligation to act [49]. VBN has proven particularly effective in predicting low-cost, habitual, or morally charged behaviours, including political engagement, support for environmental policies, and activism [41,48]. TPB, by contrast, has been widely applied to individual-level decisions in environmental behaviour and is considered especially effective at explaining high-cost behaviours, possibly owing to its incorporation of a broader range of explanatory factors [41]. Where VBN focuses more narrowly on environmental motivations, TPB adopts a wider lens. PMT, meanwhile, has been predominantly applied in disaster risk and climate change adaptation contexts, where its integration of cognitive threat appraisal and perceived capacity and desirability to act makes it particularly well-suited [52].

In sum, TPB, PMT, and VBN offer unique yet complementary lenses through which to understand individual choices and preferences as well as their drivers. This, in turn, can provide valuable insights into large-scale decision-making, such as policy development. TPB predicts volitional behaviour based on expectancy-value logic, PMT explains protective behaviours by weighing risk perceptions and coping appraisals, and VBN captures moral and identity-based motivations rooted in stable value systems. However, as all are applied within NbS preference studies, the question remains whether one theory dominates the others in terms of explanatory power, and whether studies that do not explicitly use these theories but test related variables may benefit from the structural frameworks they provide.

3. Methods and data

3.1. Literature search strategy

The review followed the ROSES RepOrting standards for Systematic Evidence Syntheses [53], which are guidelines for systematic reviews in environmental research that build upon and address shortcomings of the PRISMA guidelines (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) [54]. Following the typology of Grant and Booth [55], this review is best characterised as a systematic mapping review, combining a comprehensive and transparent search process with a tabular characterisation of explanatory variables, measurement approaches, and theoretical frameworks across included studies, supplemented by a narrative synthesis of patterns and implications.

Existing reviews [10,11,15,56] and a preselected body of relevant studies from a recent review [57], as well as non-systematic

searches in Google Scholar, helped refine the search terms used in scientific databases. This ensured that relevant peer-reviewed publications assessing preferences for NbS with an adaptation focus were systematically captured. The search included studies from 2005 to 2024, as suggested by Garcia Alvarez et al. [57]. Three categories of search terms were employed to derive studies on preferences for nature-based solutions (NbS) for climate change adaptation and (natural hazard) risk reduction. We supplemented Anderson and Renaud [10]'s search category "ways to accept" by including additional preference concepts, aiming to capture any elicitation of stated preferences towards NbS while excluding predictive modelling, simulations, and suitability studies. One category reflected NbS and various synonyms and examples thereof, as the concept is relatively novel and not consistently named as such [8,10,15]. A second category captured the adaptation and hazard risk reduction focus of NbS by including synonyms of different natural hazards and risk reduction and mitigation of these risks. To account for articles not explicitly mentioning hazards and their consequences, we also included various benefits of NbS related to adaptation and reducing climate risk, such as water retention or thermal control. While the focus was on adaptation, hazard mitigation, and risk reduction, many NbS having both functions, the distinction between climate mitigation and adaptation can be challenging [58]. Therefore, more fine-tuned decisions were made during screening. The full search string can be found in [Appendix A](#).

3.2. Screening

Title and abstract screening was conducted using ASReview (version 1.6.3), an open-source software applying active learning for systematic reviews [59]. This step was performed according to recommended standards developed for ASReview, such as the SAFE procedure [60] and snowballing according to the SYMBALS procedure [59]. Our operationalisation of NbS followed the official IUCN definition [7] and was further informed by the operationalisations proposed by Anderson and Renaud [10] and Venkataramanan et al. [15]. Following the example by Anderson and Renaud [10], we considered NbS as physical measures with a natural component during screening, distinguishing them from grey measures, which are characterised by the absence of any natural component. Articles explicitly mentioning NbS or common synonyms such as blue-green infrastructure in the context of climate adaptation or hazard risk mitigation were marked as relevant. Additionally, articles mentioning infrastructure with natural elements, such as green roofs, rain gardens, or general restoration and conservation of natural ecosystems, were included at the abstract screening stage. This way, their explicit natural hazard focus could be evaluated during full-text screening. Articles in which this criterion was not met were then excluded. This approach was deliberately adopted to avoid the premature exclusion of relevant studies that addressed NbS with a risk mitigation element without explicitly naming it as such in the abstract, as it became evident during preparation that such studies would otherwise likely have been missed. Given that NbS is a relatively novel and inconsistently labelled concept, inclusion and exclusion decisions were made on a case-by-case basis during full-text screening. We acknowledge that this approach introduces a degree of subjectivity, as the classification of NbS relied on operational definitions of constructs that are inconsistently labelled and measured across the literature, which may have affected both eligibility decisions and variable classification.

Detailed elaboration on the software, the search process, and all intermediate steps can be found in [Appendix B](#). Stepwise exclusions are illustrated in [Fig. 1](#).

The final body of literature contained 90 studies on stated preferences for NbS targeting natural hazards. Studies were included if they:

- elicited a quantitative, monetary measure of preferences, such as willingness to pay (WTP) or willingness to accept (WTA).

Fig. 1. ROSES flowchart².

- investigated the influence of social–psychological or sociodemographic explanatory variables on WTP/WTA via multivariate regression.
- explicitly mentioned a climate hazard, either in the hypothetical scenarios or as a choice attribute in the case of discrete choice experiments.

The iterative development and reasoning for these criteria can be found in [Appendix B](#).

3.3. Coding and synthesis of study data

While some general coding was done while studies were still being excluded, once the final set of studies was defined, coding was completed based on the following rules:

- Title, authors, country, stated preference method used, hazards addressed, NbS studied, theory used and details of the econometric model were reported for all studies (see supplementary database and details in [Appendix B](#)).
- The following sociodemographic variables were coded: income, age, gender, education, and distance.

² Note on final exclusions:

- No relevant explanatory variables: no explanatory variables investigated, not sufficiently connected to valuation outcomes, or only sociodemographic variables not fitting our pre-defined categories.
- Analysis out of scope: no multivariate regression analysis used.
- Method out of scope: no stated preference method used.
- Insufficient quantification of WTP: binary WTP responses without a bid level as explanatory variable.

- Social–psychological variables were re-coded according to the categories in [Table 1](#).
- Coding of direction and significance, followed a simple scheme: positive significant (+), negative significant (-), insignificant (IS), inconclusive (IN) for latent class models, where a variable determined membership to multiple classes with differing preferences.
- The cut-off for statistical significance was a p -value of 0.10 or lower.
- Variables were recoded where necessary to ensure that higher values consistently reflected greater levels of the construct (e.g., higher risk perception), making positive relationships interpretable as higher predictor levels being associated with higher outcomes.
- When multiple models showing the effect of explanatory variables on valuation were reported, the one study authors deemed to have the best fit was chosen.
- If not fully displayed, model information was inferred from the text or appendices.
- For choice experiments, attention was paid to the interaction of an explanatory variable with the ASC or the hazard attribute. If the interaction was only with a non-hazard attribute, it was assumed that the interaction with the hazard attribute was insignificant.

To assess the frequency of each variable being assessed, the following rules were applied in frequency analyses:

- For counts of each explanatory variable used, a variable was counted if it was included directly in a regression to predict WTP for an NbS, but not when only used in interactions with other explanatory variables or in correlational or descriptive analyses.

Table 1
Overview of social–psychological explanatory variables.

Variable	Explanation	Origin of concept
Risk Perception	Evaluation of the likelihood, frequency, and consequences of a hazard or climate-related risk.	Threat Appraisal [36, PMT]
Perceived Risk Reduction	Judgement of how effective an NbS is in reducing a threat.	Response Efficacy part of Coping Appraisal [36, PMT]
Hazard Experience	Extent or frequency of personal experience with a hazard event.	common PMT extension [61,62]
Risk Attitude	Willingness to engage in risky behaviour.	originating in Expected Utility Theory [63–65]
Knowledge/ Experience	Factual or experiential knowledge related to NbS and/or their benefits, any knowledge of climate change or environmental conditions that is not hazard experience.	common TPB extension; conceptualised by Kaiser et al. [50], building on Theory of Reasoned Action [42]; presently adjusted to NbS context
Environmental Attitude	Attitude toward the natural environment or toward ecological behaviour	originating in TPB [37,42] and expanded by Kaiser et al. [50] and Urban and Kaiser [66]
Environmental Behaviour	Actions intended to preserve the environment or reflecting pro-environmental attitudes.	General Ecological Behaviour [67,68]; Pro-environmental Behaviour [38,69]
Perceived Behavioural Control/ Self-Efficacy	Belief in one's ability to execute a (protective) behaviour.	Perceived Behavioural Control from TPB [46,70]; Self-Efficacy from PMT [44,71,72]
Subjective Norm	Perceived social pressure from relevant others to perform a behaviour.	TPB [37,70]
Social Variables	Grouping label capturing perceptions of the social context, such as community identity, trust in neighbours and duration of residence; full list of variables within the category can be found in the supplementary database	variable-specific; residence duration and community variables are conceptually linked to place attachment, which refers to individuals' emotional and cognitive bonds with specific locations [73]
Perceptual Variable	Perception of greenness of neighbourhood	study-specific concept from Salm et al. [31]

- If a variable was excluded from a model due to insignificance and this was explicitly stated, it was considered as having been tested, with its effect noted as insignificant.

4. Results

4.1. General descriptions of reviewed studies

Fig. 2 shows an increasing trend in NbS preference research in recent years, aligning with broader trends in NbS research in general [74,75]. No studies meeting our criteria were published before 2009. Corresponding to the review's focus on monetary stated preference studies, most studies used state-of-the-art discrete choice experiments (DCE; 57%) as their primary method for eliciting preferences [25,76], followed by contingent valuation (CV; 43%). Details on the econometric models used can be found in Appendix C.

Most studies were conducted in the United States of America (19%) and China (12%), followed by Vietnam (7%) and Italy (5%). European countries account for 36% of total studies. Fig. 3 highlights the underrepresentation of the Global South and non-Western nations, reflecting a North-centric research focus. This trend aligns with global NbS research patterns and likely results from substantial EU investments in NbS research [77,78].

As Anderson and Renaud [10] note, classifying NbS is difficult, given how broadly the term is used, authors' roles in naming the NbS, and its largely overlapping categories. Various studies have attempted to provide structure by developing operational frameworks and taxonomies [79,80], but a conclusive categorisation is still lacking.³

A wide range of NbS was investigated, with urban retention measures being the most common (17%, Fig. 4). This is followed by the

establishment of parks, green spaces and tree planting (13%) and water body renaturalisation (13%). NbS related to forest restoration, management or afforestation are addressed in 12% cases, and wetlands (10%) and mangroves (9%) are investigated frequently. While some studies investigate specific NbS measures, others examine people's attitudes towards NbS or green infrastructure in general and, therefore, do not specify concrete implementations (unspecified NbS, 6%).

In the present review, the most frequently addressed hazards in the studies are floods (42%), followed by storms (14%; including stormwater) and heat (14%). This pattern is even more pronounced in some study regions, with 51% of studies from Europe addressing floods. This aligns with data showing floods are the most costly past and future natural hazards affecting Europe [81,82].⁴

Most included studies are grounded in principles of utility maximisation, also referred to as random utility theory and Lancaster's consumer theory [83]⁵, which provide the basis for choice experiments and stated preference studies. These utility maximisation theories assume that people rationally value existing options and choose the option that yields the highest (expected) utility. These theories do not address the explanatory variables that explain preferences, which are the focus of this review, but relate to the theoretical foundation of behaviour and choice.

⁴ Original hazard labels were recoded for clarity and comparability. See supplementary database for the recoding scheme.

⁵ Studies citing Lancaster's consumer theory [83], used various labels, creating the impression that they refer to different rather than the same theory. For example, Rulleau et al. [84] call it characteristics theory, Johnson and Geisendorf [85] refer to it as the theory of demand, Zhi-Ying and Yeo-Chang [86] call it the demand characteristics theory, while Bartkowski et al. [87] refer to it as consumer theory.

³ NbS were grouped for clarity and comparability based on a recent review of NbS co-benefits [56]. See supplementary database for the recoding scheme.

Fig. 2. Distribution of studies across time and method.

Note. The studies in 2024 represent those published by the time of the literature search, September 2024.

Fig. 3. Distribution of NbS studies and hazards studied across regions.

Fig. 4. Overview of types of NbS investigated.

Table 2
Effects of social–psychological variables on WTP for NbS.

Variable	Non-theory Use				PMT		TPB/TRA + extensions				VBN + TPB	Total
	+	–	IS	IN	+	IS	+	–	IS	IN	+	
Risk Perception	22	4	15	2		2		1			1	47
Knowledge/ Experience	16		15	1				2		3	1	38
Hazard Experience	13	1	17	1	1	1						34
Env. Attitude	13	1	5	1			7	1	1	3	1	33
Env. Behaviour	12		3									15
Perceived Risk Reduction	7	1	2						1			11
Perceived Beh. Control/ Self-efficacy	1		1				5			1		8
Subjective Norm							4	1	2			7
Risk Attitude	2	1										3
Social Variables ^a	6	2	9									17
Perceptual Variables		2										2

Note. Variables are coded so that higher values indicate greater levels of the underlying construct. Positive coefficients reflect higher predictor levels associated with higher WTP.

^a Positive effects: residence duration (2), trust in government (2), neighbourhood trust (1), livelihood dependence on mangroves (1). Negative effects: residence duration (1), state responsibility for hazard protection (1). See supplementary database for all effects.

4.2. Variable patterns and theory use

Among the reviewed studies, social–psychological explanatory variables of NbS preferences comprise 215 observations across 74 studies. However, only 11 of these 74 studies explicitly refer to a theory. The remaining 63 studies include such variables but rely solely on previous empirical research for justification, forming a chain of studies with a limited theoretical foundation. The Theory of Planned Behaviour and its predecessor, the Theory of Reasoned Action [37,88], as well as their extensions, are the most frequently used theories (TPB; n = 10). Additional theories underlying model construction and explanatory variables include the Value-Belief-Norm Theory [24, VBN], employed by one study that also utilised TPB, and the Protection Motivation Theory [36, PMT; n = 1].

Although most social–psychological variables investigated can be grouped into a few broad categories, the direction and significance of their relationships with preferences vary. Table 2 reveals general patterns of relationships between explanatory variables and WTP for NbS across the reviewed studies. Specifically, factors predominantly associated with higher WTP for NbS include higher risk perception, greater knowledge of or more experience with NbS and their benefits, a greater degree of hazard experience, and more positive environmental attitudes. These patterns largely align with theoretical expectations that higher levels of these constructs drive support for and acceptance of adaptation and NbS.

Within the PMT framework, higher risk perception and perceived risk reduction are expected to increase motivation to engage in protective actions [36]. The dominance of positive, significant results largely confirms this relationship. Likewise, effects of variables related to TPB, namely environmental attitude, perceived behavioural control/self-efficacy, and subjective norm, mainly confirm the theory’s predictions of positive relationships [37]. However, considering that self-efficacy has been identified as a strong predictor of climate adaptation behaviour [6], the number of studies investigating this variable is small. While not directly related to a specific theory, the predominantly positive effects of hazard experience and greater knowledge or

experience with NbS align with the broader scientific field. The meta-analysis by van Valkengoed and Steg [6] showed that research has paid inflated attention to the role of knowledge and experience in explaining adaptation behaviour, while their effects are moderate at best. This may also explain why the number of insignificant findings for these two variables is relatively high.

While most relationships confirm expectations, some results on social–psychological variables reveal unexpected effects. Although a substantial number of insignificant results are reported, these tend to be outnumbered by the confirmatory effects. What stands out is the near absence of studies reporting significant negative relationships that contradict theoretical expectations. In addition, there appears to be little difference in these patterns between studies that employ theory and those that do not, although the small number of theory-based studies limits the strength of this comparison. Within the only study explicitly referring to PMT, the effect of risk perception is insignificant. The relationship between environmental attitude is significant in both theory-based and non-theory studies, but fewer articles utilise the theory. While perceived risk reduction can be attributed to PMT, the only PMT-based study does not include that variable, so no comparison can be made. Likewise, while perceived behavioural control from TPB is reflected in PMT’s self-efficacy construct, only theory studies using TPB explicitly test and confirm the variable’s effect. Similarly, only TPB studies investigate and confirm the role of subjective norms.

Many studies without an explicit theoretical basis still investigate constructs from theories such as PMT and TPB, such as risk perception or environmental attitude. While the lack of explicit mention of these theories does not necessarily impact the validity of individual findings, it does mean that the reasoning behind construct selection is not made transparent, which has implications for comparability and cumulative knowledge building. These implications will be discussed in more detail in the Discussion.

In addition to social–psychological variables, most studies utilise sociodemographic variables to explain WTP for NbS. Their direction and significance are displayed in Table 3. Only higher income and

Table 3
Effects of sociodemographic variables on WTP for NbS.

Variable	+	-	IS	IN	Total
Income	43	5	27	6	81
Age	11	25	34	4	74
Gender	14	9	37	5	65
Education	34	2	26	4	66
Distance	1	10	13	4	28

Note. 1 = female, 0 = male. Other variables are coded so that higher values indicate greater levels of the underlying construct. Positive coefficients reflect higher predictor levels associated with higher WTP.

education predict higher WTP across a relatively large number of studies, followed by a substantial, but smaller number of insignificant results. For age, gender and distance, insignificant results are more frequent than significant ones. Still, the significant patterns suggest that younger individuals, women, and those living closer to the valued resource tend to report higher WTP.

Although no review has yet systematically examined how sociodemographic factors shape stated preferences for NbS, ample economic theory has established the dynamics of income and income elasticity of WTP for environmental goods in particular [21,89]. Higher-income individuals may have more disposable resources to allocate to environmental goods and services, including NbS [90]. Despite mixed evidence [91], the sensitivity of WTP to income is often viewed as an indicator of measure validity [92], supporting the plausibility of this link. Older individuals tend to report lower WTP for environmental goods [93], though findings on age-related differences in environmental concern are inconsistent [94]. Our review aligns with Gelissen [95], who found that income, (age), and education influence support for environmental protection, and with Han and Kuhlicke [11], who highlight the roles of economic conditions and education in NbS perceptions.

Although we considered only direct effects, other mechanisms warrant further attention. Interaction effects likely shape these relationships to some degree. For example, women often exhibit higher risk perception [96,97] and stronger environmental attitudes and behaviours [98–100], which may explain higher WTP. Life-course patterns may also be non-linear, with environmental concern peaking in youth, dipping in midlife, and rising again later in life [93,101]. Accounting for such non-linearities could enhance explanatory power beyond standard logistic specifications.

4.3. Operationalisation of social–psychological variables

Upon examining the operationalisation and measurement of variables in the studies, significant variation exists (Table 4). Both binary and single-item Likert scales, as well as more complex multi-item Likert scales and composite scores, are used. Some studies used counts, frequency items, proxies or categorical variables (see supplementary database for details on all variables and their operationalisation). Within the variable categories, not only do the measurement scales differ, but also the scope of the questions varies. For example, risk perception is conceptualised for both specific hazards and climate/environmental hazards in general. Likewise, for environmental attitudes, some studies ask about general attitudes towards the environment, while others elicit specific attitudes regarding the payment for NbS or specific environmental services. We also observe variation in the use of objective and subjective measures. For example, some studies use objective knowledge scales or the quantification of damage caused by hazards. In addition, most studies use self-rated subjective measures for most variables. The use of standardised psychometric scales applicable across diverse contexts is scarce, such as the New Environmental Paradigm to measure environmental attitudes or the Risk Attitude Scale (Table 4). Most studies rely on context-specific, self-made items and scales. While some studies adapt scales from existing research,

substantial variation remains, limiting systematic comparisons and the generalisability of observed relationships.

Overall, while we cannot make conclusive claims on causal relationships between variable operationalisation and study outcomes, some general patterns can be identified. Despite the range of measurements, from simple single-item to more complex multi-item composite scores, a majority of studies appear to rely on simple single-item measurements for their variable operationalisation. While one might expect more sophisticated measures to produce significant effects more consistently, no such patterns are observed. Significant expectation-confirming and insignificant results, as well as significant results opposing empirical expectations, appeared across the full range of measurement sophistication (see supplementary database for details). Nevertheless, the results in Table 4 provide a valuable overview of the current state of the field and a foundation for advancing the integration of social–psychological explanatory variables in stated preference research. A key next step is to establish standardised practices, including the use of rigorously tested and validated scales where available, and to prioritise their development where rigour and validation are lacking.

5. Discussion

This review of stated preference studies on nature-based solutions (NbS) for climate adaptation reveals a research landscape investigating many explanatory variables of preferences measured in diverse ways. As a result, it becomes difficult to compare findings or draw general conclusions about which determinants most strongly influence preferences. Nonetheless, this review provides key findings that extend those of prior reviews [10,11] to the stated preference context by especially focusing on social–psychological predictors of NbS preferences. It also offers insights into the operationalisation and measurement of explanatory factors and examines theory use. Four main findings and their practical implications emerge.

First, across studies, there is diversity in the variables used, and there are clear patterns in which of these variables show significant effects. Risk perception, knowledge/experience, hazard experience, and environmental attitude emerge as the most frequently investigated and significant social–psychological variables, substantially adding to the understanding of stated preferences for NbS beyond sociodemographic variables alone. However, the prominence of certain variables may partially reflect research trends rather than predictive superiority, as the qualitative nature of this review does not allow such quantifications. As noted by van Valkengoed and Steg [6], constructs such as knowledge and experience receive disproportionate attention in the adaptation field, even though their effects are generally small to moderate, while constructs showing stronger effects, including self-efficacy, norms, and negative affect, remain underexplored. Similar patterns appear in the reviewed stated preference studies on NbS. While many studies examine knowledge and experience, fewer investigate self-efficacy and perceived behavioural control, or perceived risk reduction. Likewise, the neglect of social and group-level dynamics observed in general adaptation research is mirrored here [35], with limited attention to

Table 4
Operationalisation of social–psychological variables.

Variable	Operationalisation	
	Single item	Multi-item
Risk Perception	<p>Binary (or ≤ 3-category) concern/awareness/likelihood of specific hazard: [30,102–110]</p> <p>Binary concern of climate change in general: [111,112]</p> <p>Likert-scale rating of specific hazard likelihood/concern or perception of environmental condition: [107,110,113–120]</p> <p>Proxy variable: [121]</p>	<p>Composite score from Likert-scale items [122–129]</p>
Knowledge/Experience	<p>Subjective binary (or ≤ 3-category) knowledge: [30,32,85,104,111,117,130–136]</p> <p>Subjective Likert-scale knowledge assessment: [87,128]</p> <p>Frequency scale of experience: [87,137]</p> <p>Binary/categorical (≤ 3) experience: [30,138,139]</p> <p>Binary indicator per experience: [121]</p> <p>Count of experience: [140,141]</p> <p>Objective single-select knowledge question (one correct): [142]</p>	<p>Objective knowledge tests: [110,129,143–145]</p> <p>Subjective Likert-scale knowledge assessment: [146]</p>
Hazard Experience	<p>Binary experience specific hazard: [106–108,128,133,134,147–149]</p> <p>Likert-scale recency within timeframe: [87]</p> <p>Count experience specific hazard: [114,150,151]</p> <p>Quantified revenue or crop loss: [116,152]</p> <p>Categorical variable of 3+ categories: [30,116,153]</p> <p>Other: combination of indicators into one [113], open question [103], multi-select:[110]</p>	
Environmental Attitude	<p>Binary indicator of general attitude: [103,105,108,111–113,135]</p> <p>Binary indicator of attitude towards payment: [130,154]</p> <p>Likert-scale general attitude: [32,85,115,117,118]</p>	<p>Composite score/complex measures: [127,129,143,145,155–158]</p> <p>NEP scale: [85,134,144,159,160]</p>
Environmental Behaviour	<p>Binary membership/donations to organisations: [87,104,107,113,148,161–164]</p> <p>Binary indicators for other behaviours: [122,165]</p> <p>Likert-scale frequency of specific behaviour: [131]</p>	<p>Likert-scale frequency of various behaviours: [128]</p>
Perceived Risk Reduction	<p>Likert-scale effectiveness/provision of protective benefits: [110,115,122,128,166]</p> <p>Binary/categorical indicator: [105,149]</p> <p>Multiple-choice question: [115]</p>	<p>Subjective Likert-scale/composite score: [124,157]</p>
Perceived Behavioural Control/Self-efficacy	<p>Binary item: [32,104,133]</p>	<p>Behaviour-specific composite score from Likert-scale items: [85,143,145,157,158]</p>
Subjective Norm	<p>Binary item: [32]</p>	<p>Composite score from Likert-scale items: [85,143,145,157,158]</p>
Risk Attitude	<p>Likert-scale risk-taking (0 = “completely unwilling”, 10 = “very willing”): [120,133,134]</p>	

Note. The social and perceptual variables categories were omitted from this overview, as they include heterogeneous constructs and only one variable, respectively. Details on their operationalisations and those of all other variables are available in the supplementary database.

constructs such as community cohesion, place dependence, or interpersonal trust. Compounding this uneven coverage, variable measurement shows considerable variety across studies, yet no discernible links between measurement approach and observed relationships are apparent. The frequent use of context-specific, self-made items rather than validated instruments limits systematic comparison and generalisability, even when conceptually similar constructs are examined. To improve comparability and robustness, future studies should therefore employ systematic validated measurement tools that are sufficiently general to account for contextual heterogeneity while maintaining conceptual consistency with targeted behaviours [50]. Adopting measurement

standards from psychology and related disciplines can help address this empirical fragmentation. Future research should also expand the range of social–psychological variables examined, with greater attention to previously neglected constructs and those capturing the collective nature of many NbS. They may draw on insights from related disciplines to identify underexplored factors and inform alternative modelling approaches, such as interactions. Future meta-analytical work is needed to quantify relationships and robustly identify the most influential determinants of heterogeneity in WTP for NbS.

Secondly, very few studies apply theories to guide the selection of explanatory variables, and the variety of theories used is limited.

The general lack of explicit theory use identified by Han and Kuhlicke [11] and Kuhlicke et al. [35] thus also applies to our review. Many studies still assess constructs that originate from existing theories, without explicitly citing them. While explicit theory use does not per se guarantee stronger or more reliable results, it can contribute to the quality of empirical studies in different ways. Theories can provide a transparent basis for construct selection and operationalisation, making design choices visible and open to evaluation [35]. This transparency supports cross-study comparability, which underpins benefit transfer and quantitative synthesis [33]. Where theory clarifies not only which variables are included but also why they matter, it can support the identification of concrete intervention levers for behavioural change [167]. Without an explicit theoretical basis, findings are harder to integrate into a cumulative evidence base, and studies cannot contribute to theory development or falsification [35]. Despite these reasons for the value of theory, some limitations apply in the context of our review. Protection-Motivation Theory, Theory of Planned Behaviour and Value-Belief Norm Theory were developed to explain behaviour rather than monetary valuation, which may explain their limited uptake in this literature. Additionally, in highly context-specific settings, no single framework may provide a perfect fit, and imposing a theoretical structure can in some cases constrain empirical innovation [35]. The aim should therefore not be theory use for its own sake, but rather a more deliberate and transparent engagement with frameworks, including explicit justification of construct selection and operationalisation.

Third, building on this, our review shows that both PMT and TPB capture important determinants of NbS preferences but may overlook additional relevant constructs, pointing to the value of theory extensions and integrations noted by Kuhlicke et al. [35]. Combining elements of both theories may therefore be beneficial, such as adding attitude to PMT [168] or incorporating risk perceptions into TPB [169–171]. Bagheri and Emami [172] provide support for combining PMT and TPB variables, whereas Wang et al. [173] identify mediation effects highlighting the interplay of constructs. Our review also identifies several additional variables influencing NbS preferences that fall outside PMT and TPB but can be incorporated into them. Hazard experience can be integrated into PMT's threat appraisal, as shown in flood adaptation studies [61,62]. Knowledge and experience with NbS may also be incorporated into PMT and TPB, though their integration in stated preference work remains limited. A study beyond the stated preference literature adds knowledge of natural hazards to a combined PMT-TPB model [174], suggesting future studies to further explore this.

Although PMT and TPB are well established, their predominant use may hinder theoretical innovation [175]. By contrast, a broader set of frameworks is used outside the stated preference literature. Many studies were excluded from this review due to methodological criteria, and these studies draw on a wider range of behavioural and social theories. For example, Carlet [176] combines the Diffusion of Innovation theory [177], the Technology Acceptance Model [178], and General Organisational Theory [179] to explain attitudes toward adopting green infrastructure in local governments. Murtagh and Frost [180] draw from Self-Determination theory [181] to highlight the role of intrinsic motivation in adopting urban front gardens. Wong et al. [182] apply the push-pull framework [183], originally from tourism and leisure studies, to explain urban green space visitation as a climate adaptation strategy. Finally, Han et al. [184] integrate PMT with the Protective Action Decision Model [185,186] to develop the Place-based Risk Appraisal Model (PRAM) for explaining public attitudes toward NbS for flood risk reduction.

This broader theoretical landscape illustrates how stated preference research could benefit from greater theoretical diversity, with a wider range of frameworks providing structure where established theories seem insufficient. As van Valkengoed et al. [187] argue, theory and practical impact are not competing priorities but synergistic. Theories not only offer a framework for structuring and integrating evidence, but also provide information on the antecedents of behaviour that are

critical to developing effective interventions [187,188]. In the context of stated preference studies on NbS, this means that theory should not only extend scientific knowledge by building on and refining existing frameworks [35] but also enhance the interpretability and policy relevance of WTP estimates. Following best-practice guidelines [88] and openly sharing datasets and survey instruments will further facilitate replication and cumulative progress.

Fourth, translating these findings into practice, the social-psychological factors identified in this review represent promising and actionable targets for public engagement, planning, and policy decisions surrounding NbS. Because NbS are typically implemented at the local level, insights into the social-psychological determinants of preferences are particularly valuable for informing where and how such measures are introduced. Risk perception and hazard experience are among the most frequent and consistent predictors of NbS preferences, suggesting that communication strategies emphasising locally relevant hazard risks and the protective benefits of NbS may be particularly effective, especially in communities with recent hazard experience. Framing NbS as concrete responses to personally salient risks, rather than abstract environmental interventions, may increase perceived relevance and strengthen support for NbS. Knowledge of NbS and their functions also emerges as a consistent predictor of WTP, motivating campaigns that focus on developing such knowledge among the public, with particular attention to the specific functions of NbS, such as their effectiveness in reducing risk and their co-benefits for biodiversity and wellbeing. The constructs less frequently assessed in the reviewed studies, including community cohesion, place identity, and interpersonal trust, may further shape how NbS are received at the local level and deserve both further empirical investigation and attention in participatory planning processes. Likewise, where self-efficacy and perceived behavioural control are found to matter, engagement strategies could focus on reducing barriers and increasing confidence in NbS adoption, while campaigns targeting perceived efficacy may benefit from fostering a sense that individual and collective action through NbS can make a meaningful difference. Beyond communication, the sociodemographic predictors identified in the reviewed studies also carry implications for planning and implementation decisions. Evidence that distance to NbS shapes preferences underscores the relevance of spatial targeting in NbS placement. Where income emerges as a significant predictor, this has implications for the distributional aspects of NbS financing. If lower-income individuals consistently report lower willingness to pay, it may be worth considering income-sensitive payment schemes for NbS financing. Although stated preference methods capture preferences rather than behaviours, the psychological mechanisms they uncover may nonetheless inform behavioural interventions and demand-side strategies for NbS. Drawing from environmental and social psychology in designing such interventions may assist in selecting theoretically grounded yet practically impactful targets [167,188].

These insights should be interpreted in light of several caveats regarding the WTP and WTA estimates on which they are based. The first concerns the concept of warm-glow. Andreoni [189] demonstrated that individuals derive utility not only from the provision of a public good itself, but from the act of contributing to it, a phenomenon termed "impure altruism". This is closely related to Kahneman and Knetsch [190]'s argumentation that responses in contingent valuation studies may reflect WTP for the moral satisfaction of contributing to a public good, rather than the economic value of the good per se. Relatedly, Bouma and Koetse [191] find empirically that warm-glow feelings and social expectations about others' behaviour are significant drivers of hypothetical bias, inflating stated donations relative to actual ones, and that the factors explaining stated WTP differ substantially from those predicting revealed behaviour. This aligns with broader meta-analytic evidence that respondents overstate their actual willingness to pay by a factor of approximately three in hypothetical settings, with the degree of bias varying across elicitation methods and good types [192]. These considerations mean that WTP and WTA estimates may deviate from

the true economic value of the goods being valued, and should not be interpreted as equivalent to policy support. The payment vehicles used to elicit values, such as entrance fees or voluntary contributions, are often not aligned with specific policy instruments, further widening the gap between stated values and real-world policy preferences. WTP and WTA are therefore best understood as preference and value indicators, capable of informing policy design, but not as direct measures of financial or policy support. Finally, by design, the methods employed in the reviewed studies focus on financial contributions and therefore tend to exclude younger populations, usually under the age of 18. This is a meaningful limitation, as children and adolescents constitute an important part of society whose preferences are rarely captured. In addition, they are among the primary beneficiaries of NbS, since the effects of measures often take time to manifest and thus disproportionately benefit future generations [193]. Although some studies on young adults' preferences have been conducted [194,195], the empirical work reviewed does not adequately account for this group and younger individuals. Future research should explore methodological approaches that allow for their preferences to be included.

Taken together, these findings call for more deliberate construct selection, standardised measurement, explicit theoretical engagement, and stronger links between stated preference research and other scientific disciplines, advances that would improve both the scientific comparability and the practical relevance of NbS valuation studies.

6. Conclusion

This review synthesises evidence from 90 peer-reviewed studies that apply stated preference methods to assess public preferences for NbS for climate adaptation and hazard risk reduction. In contrast to previous related reviews, this study focuses on the determinants of willingness to pay (WTP) and offers detailed insights into the drivers shaping people's valuation of NbS. Beyond identifying which factors matter, the review investigates how these determinants are operationalised across studies and the extent to which they are grounded in theory.

The synthesis reveals that both sociodemographic and social-psychological variables influence WTP. Income, education, and age play a role, but psychological and experiential factors, such as risk perception, hazard experience, environmental attitudes, and knowledge, consistently predict higher WTP for NbS. While risk perception has long been recognised as a key factor in climate adaptation decisions, our review extends this knowledge by highlighting the role of environmental attitudes when adaptation involves NbS. Our findings further corroborate existing evidence showing that potentially relevant variables have thus far received limited attention, such as those related to efficacy beliefs and social processes surrounding the collective character of NbS implementation.

A major takeaway of this review is that the field remains theoretically and methodologically fragmented. Many studies rely on ad hoc variable selection and context-specific measures, which limit comparability and the cumulative building of knowledge. Addressing this gap requires the systematic use of validated instruments, diversification of theoretical approaches, and stronger integration of social, motivational, and contextual variables. Enhanced transparency through data and instrument sharing would further strengthen replicability and enable quantitative meta-analyses.

Overall, this review advances understanding of the factors that shape citizens' valuation of NbS and consolidates the explanatory variables commonly examined in the empirical literature. By highlighting both well-established and underexplored determinants, it offers a foundation for designing future studies. Such research should combine methodological rigour, through the systematic use of validated instruments and more consistent application of theoretical frameworks, with attention to the social dynamics surrounding NbS. As emphasised across this review, WTP and WTA estimates, as welfare measures, reflect individual preferences and the values people assign to non-market

goods, rather than direct support for specific policies. Strengthening methodological alignment will nonetheless support the more effective integration of these individual perspectives into climate adaptation policy and practice, by providing a clearer evidence base on which policy relevant decisions about NbS can be grounded.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Magdalena Lesch: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Teun Schrieks:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Mark J. Koetse:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **W.J. Wouter Botzen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Search categories for database queries

See [Table A.1](#).

Appendix B. Details on search, screening and study coding

B.1. ASReview and SAFE procedure

ASReview's machine learning algorithm trains a prediction model based on a reviewer's labelling decisions of abstracts. Learning from these decisions, it predicts relevance scores and thereby repeatedly reorders the stack of to-be-labelled records, with records of higher relevance moving to the front of the stack. The researcher then labels the record at the first position as relevant or irrelevant. This record is transferred to the training set, where the decision continuously improves the model's relevance prediction and reorders the stack of records. This way, relevant records can be detected quicker, saving up to 92% of screening time [196,197], without the need to screen up to 95% of total records, as opposed to classical systematic reviews [59]. The results of a broader search, such as the one in the present case, can be screened more quickly, with limited risk of excluding relevant papers. In supplement to ASReview, Boetje and van de Schoot [60] established the SAFE procedure, which constitutes guidelines for the screening of abstracts. It suggests screening in four stages, using different algorithms for detecting relevant articles, heuristics for stopping screening within stages and cross-validation by a second screener. Based on their validated stopping rules and the active learning process, a relatively large body of potentially relevant studies could be considered, as the procedure does not necessitate screening all articles before the majority of relevant articles can be identified with high confidence [196]. The SAFE procedure was supplemented with snowballing according to the SYMBALS procedure [198].

B.2. Search and screening details

Due to the use of active learning and the SAFE procedure, a broad search was conducted, with a few exclusions of irrelevant research fields ([Table A.1](#), [Appendix A](#)). The search in both search engines excluded review studies and those in languages other than English. The total number of abstracts imported into ASReview after deduplication was 34,224. This final set of articles was produced on September 9th, 2024. Following the SAFE procedure, abstract screening was stopped at 492 abstracts labelled as relevant. Screening of abstracts was done

Table A.1
Search strings used in Scopus and Web of Science databases.

Search category	Scopus (TITLE-ABS-KEY)	Web of Science (TS=)
Nature-Based Solutions [10,15]	("Nature-based solution*" OR "Nature based solution*" OR "Ecosystem*" PRE/1 (solution* OR adaptation OR mitigation OR approach* OR service* OR management*)) OR ("Green*" PRE/1 (infrastructure* OR space* OR roof* OR corridor* OR wall* OR street* OR building*)) OR ("Blue*" PRE/1 (infrastructure* OR space* OR roof*)) OR ("Natur*" PRE/1 (infrastructure* OR roof* OR capital* OR restoration* OR conservation* OR protection*)) OR ("Ecol*" PRE/1 (adaptation OR mitigation OR corridor* OR restor* OR engineer*)) OR eco-engineer* OR ecoengineer* OR BGI* OR NBS* OR nbs OR "building with nature" OR "low impact development*" OR "low impact infrastructure*" OR "permeable pavement*" OR bioswale OR "urban wetland" OR "natural water retention measure*" OR "urban drainage system*" OR "vegetated buffer strip*" OR "water retention pond*" OR "integrated coastal zone management*" OR "integrated water resource management*" OR "urban green*" OR "urban riparian corridor*" OR "riparian buffer strip*" OR "rain garden" OR raingarden* OR "urban park*" OR "urban forest*" OR mangrove* OR bioswale* OR saltmarsh* OR "nature-inclusive farming*" OR "nature inclusive farming*" OR "farmer-managed natural regeneration*" OR "farmer managed natural regeneration*")	((("Nature-based solution*" OR "Nature based solution*" OR "Ecosystem*" NEAR/1 (solution* OR adaptation OR mitigation OR approach* OR service* OR management*)) OR ("Green*" NEAR/1 (infrastructure* OR space* OR roof* OR corridor* OR wall* OR street* OR building*)) OR ("Blue*" NEAR/1 (infrastructure* OR space* OR roof*)) OR ("Natur*" NEAR/1 (infrastructure* OR roof* OR capital* OR restoration* OR conservation* OR protection*)) OR ("Ecol*" NEAR/1 (adaptation OR mitigation OR corridor* OR restor* OR engineer*)) OR eco-engineer* OR ecoengineer* OR BGI* OR NBS* OR nbs OR "building with nature" OR "low impact development*" OR "low impact infrastructure*" OR "permeable pavement*" OR bioswale OR "urban wetland" OR "natural water retention measure*" OR "urban drainage system*" OR "vegetated buffer strip*" OR "water retention pond*" OR "integrated coastal zone management*" OR "integrated water resource management*" OR "urban green*" OR "urban riparian corridor*" OR "riparian buffer strip*" OR "rain garden" OR raingarden* OR "urban park*" OR "urban forest*" OR mangrove* OR bioswale* OR saltmarsh* OR "nature-inclusive farming*" OR "nature inclusive farming*" OR "farmer-managed natural regeneration*" OR "farmer managed natural regeneration*"))
Acceptance/Preference [10,11]	(accept* OR aware* OR perce* OR participat* OR prefer* OR buy-in* OR evaluat* OR opinion* OR sentiment OR attitude OR belief OR behavio* OR apath* OR indifferen* OR burnout OR fatigue OR reject* OR "willingness to pay*" OR wtp OR "willingness to accept*" OR wta OR "willingness to volunteer*" OR wtv OR "willingness to work*" OR view OR willingness)	(accept* OR aware* OR perce* OR participat* OR prefer* OR buy-in* OR evaluat* OR opinion* OR sentiment OR attitude OR belief OR behavio* OR apath* OR indifferen* OR burnout OR fatigue OR reject* OR "willingness to pay*" OR wtp OR "willingness to accept*" OR wta OR "willingness to volunteer*" OR wtv OR "willingness to work*" OR view OR willingness)
Hazard & Risk Reduction [11,56]	((("hazard*" OR disaster* OR risk*) PRE/1 (mitigation* OR adjustment* OR reduction* OR management* OR adaptation*)) OR disaster* OR hazard* OR climate* OR "climate change*" OR "natural disaster*" OR flood* OR inundation* OR "storm wave*" OR "storm surge*" OR "tidal surge*" OR "storm tide*" OR "hurricane tide*" OR "tropical surge*" OR drought* OR heat* OR heatwave* OR "extreme heat*" OR landslide* OR mudslide* OR mudflow* OR rockslide* OR "debris flow*" OR tsunami* OR "seismic sea wave*" OR bushfire* OR wildfire* OR "forest fire*" OR stormwater* OR storm* OR rainfall* OR erosion OR typhoon* OR cyclone* OR "sea level rise*" OR "water scarcity*" OR hail* OR "extreme precipitation*" OR "extreme weather*" OR avalanche OR (pluv* OR coast* OR meteo* OR hydro* OR flood* OR "climate change*" OR climate* OR disaster* OR natural* OR environmental*) AND (risk OR hazard)) OR regulat* OR "water retention*" OR runoff* OR "sea level rise*" OR temperature* OR resilien* OR "water quality*" OR "air quality*" OR carbon* OR cool* OR "thermal control*" OR "thermal regulation*" OR pollution OR "soil quality*" OR "soil quality*" OR "pest control*"))	((("hazard*" OR disaster*" OR risk*") NEAR/1 (mitigation* OR adjustment* OR reduction* OR management* OR adaptation*)) OR disaster* OR hazard* OR climate* OR "climate change*" OR "natural disaster*" OR flood* OR inundation* OR "storm wave*" OR "storm surge*" OR "tidal surge*" OR "storm tide*" OR "hurricane tide*" OR "tropical surge*" OR drought* OR heat* OR heatwave* OR "extreme heat*" OR landslide* OR mudslide* OR mudflow* OR rockslide* OR "debris flow*" OR tsunami* OR "seismic sea wave*" OR bushfire* OR wildfire* OR "forest fire*" OR stormwater* OR storm* OR rainfall* OR erosion OR typhoon* OR cyclone* OR "sea level rise*" OR "water scarcity*" OR hail* OR "extreme precipitation*" OR "extreme weather*" OR avalanche OR (pluv* OR coast* OR meteo* OR hydro* OR flood* OR "climate change*" OR climate* OR disaster* OR natural* OR environmental*) AND (risk OR hazard)) OR regulat* OR "water retention*" OR runoff* OR "sea level rise*" OR temperature* OR resilien* OR "water quality*" OR "air quality*" OR carbon* OR cool* OR "thermal control*" OR "thermal regulation*" OR pollution OR "soil quality*" OR "soil quality*" OR "pest control*"))
Exclusions/Specifications	AND PUBYEAR >2004 AND PUBYEAR <=2026 AND (LIMIT-TO(DOCTYPE, "ar")) AND (EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "PHAR") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "IMMU") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "VETE") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "NEUR") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "NURS") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "HEAL") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "DENT") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "BIOC") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "MEDI") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "CHEM") OR EXCLUDE(SUBJAREA, "PHYS")) AND (LIMIT-TO(LANGUAGE, "English"))	AND DT=(Article) AND LA=(English) NOT TS=("alternative medicine*" OR "childhood development*" OR "cleft lip" OR "e. coli" OR "mental illness*" OR "search and rescue" OR "stress management*" OR "technological disaster*" OR abusive OR ageing OR aging OR alcohol* OR Alzheimer OR anaerobic OR antibiotic OR antidepressant* OR anxiety OR arts OR autoreceptor* OR biology OR cancer* OR cardiovascular OR cell* OR caribu OR circumcision OR coal* OR contaminat* OR customer* OR dance* OR dementia OR depression OR diabetes OR diamorphine OR digestates OR disease* OR drug* OR electricity OR electromagnetic OR emergency OR entrepreneurship OR evacuation OR e-waste* OR fracking OR fukushima OR hernia OR hiv OR hunting OR infant OR influenza OR injur* OR invertebrate OR macaque OR medical OR medication* OR metabolic OR mice OR microbial OR milk OR min* OR myopia OR newborn* OR nurse* OR oil* OR oxytocin OR pain OR particulate OR patient* OR pediatric OR pension OR petrochemical* OR phenotype* OR phosphorus OR physician* OR physiological OR poaching OR prenatal OR prophylaxis OR psychiatric OR psychosis OR "public housing*" OR radiation* OR radon OR railway* OR resuscitat* OR robot* OR rodent* OR sarcoma OR sexual OR sleep OR stutter OR suicide OR surgeon* OR surgical OR symptom* OR terrorism OR terrorist* OR thermoplastic OR ticks OR trpm2 OR UAV OR vaccine)

based on the recommended SAFE procedure [60]. In Phase 1, a random subsample of 1% (n = 342) of the total number of records was used as a training set to estimate the expected number of relevant documents in the total dataset. The random sample was obtained using Rayyan software. Then, the fraction of relevant records in the training set (FRR_t = 0005; 2/342) could be multiplied by the total number of records (T) to obtain an estimate of relevant records in the total dataset (RR_T = 200). This estimate was used in the second phase of the SAFE procedure as a stopping heuristic for screening.

In phase 2 of SAFE, a relatively simple active learning model (Naïve Bayes) and feature extractor (TF-IDF) were trained based on the labelled training set from Phase 1 and three additional preselected records that had been identified as capturing the review target particularly well. This was done in ASReview (version 1.6.3). Both qualitative and quantitative results were marked as relevant to gain richer insights

into the field and to nuance the discussion. Screening in this phase was stopped based on four mutually independent heuristics: All key papers (= predetermined as relevant) have been marked as relevant, at least twice the RR_T records (400) have been screened, a minimum of 10% of the total dataset (3422) was screened, and no relevant records have been identified in the last 200 records [60]. ASReview further provides a recall plot in which the number of relevant records is plotted against the number of reviewed records. This allows for detecting a plateau in screening, indicating that many irrelevant records have been screened in a row and that the probability of identifying further relevant records is small. In the present context, screening was stopped once all stopping conditions were fulfilled. This was at 3459 labelled records and 554 relevant records identified. This number also included qualitative studies (n = 77), which were removed from the dataset once Phase 2 was concluded. This way, the classification model in Phase 3

would only be trained on the quantitative results, which made up the review's core.

An additional check of included records from Phase 2 was done to verify the decisions made and to exclude any wrongfully included articles. This resulted in the exclusion of 34 articles that were incorrectly included, with most of them not focusing on the hazard reduction aspects of NbS. Thus, 442 articles labelled as relevant were used for training the model in the next phase. Phase 3 suggests switching to a more complex active learning model to reorder remaining records based on different criteria, which may allow the detection of slightly different relevant records. ASReview is currently the only software supporting such model switching. As recommended, the integrated Random Forest model and Doc2Vec feature extractor were used in ASReview. The labelled dataset including only the quantitative relevant results from Phase 2 is used to train the new model, which reordered the unlabelled records according to its new algorithm. Again, a stopping rule for screening was applied here, namely, stopping after having screened 200 irrelevant records in a row. This led to the screening of an additional 1116 records and the identification of 26 additional relevant records. Thus, the total number of relevant records after Phase 3 was 468.

Screening in phases 1–3 was based on the same criteria. Active learning works best when the decision made by the researcher follows strict criteria, leading to unambiguous inclusions and exclusions and allowing the model to learn and predict optimally. Therefore, in the present case, articles explicitly mentioning an NbS for climate adaptation or risk mitigation were marked as relevant, such as NbS specifically targeting a climate-related hazard or a benefit of reducing risks or consequences of such hazards. Additionally, articles mentioning natural infrastructure, such as green roofs, rain gardens, and natural ecosystems (e.g., forests or wetlands), were included if they assessed the preferences of human subjects towards their regulating ecosystem services, or an explicit natural hazard. This way, during full-text screening, whether the NbS addressed the risk of natural hazards or their consequences could be evaluated. If not, such articles were excluded from further analysis. In preparation for the search, this was done as it became evident that some studies investigated NbS with a risk mitigation element but did not explicitly mention this aspect or the hazard in the abstract. If this had been an inclusion requirement at the first stage, various relevant articles would likely have been missed.

Quality assessment was conducted in Phase 4 of SAFE, the final phase, which aimed to identify any previously unidentified relevant records. For this, a simple model (Naïve Bayes) and feature extractor (TF-IDF) were used on the previously labelled as irrelevant articles. The active learning model in this phase was trained based on the ten articles with the highest and lowest relevance scores in the validation mode of ASReview. A second reviewer then identified any relevant but previously excluded records. A stopping rule of 50 consecutive irrelevant records was applied. This resulted in the identification of nine additional relevant records.

Additional relevant records were identified using backwards citation tracking, applying the SYMBALS procedure in ASReview [198]. This process identifies additional relevant records based on the reference list of relevant studies. Specifically, backwards snowballing was applied to the 15 most relevant studies identified in Phase 3 to limit the additional screening time. This method aims to compensate for the shortcomings of automated screening processes, such as active learning, which tend to miss a small fraction of relevant articles, by combining them with backwards snowballing. Further, SYMBALS complements broad searches and allows for less-than-perfect search strings, as wrongfully included and wrongfully excluded papers are minimised by active learning and backwards snowballing, respectively. This led to screening 730 additional records and identifying 15 additional articles to be considered at full text. Following the SAFE process, the final body of relevant abstracts was double-checked to remove incorrectly included studies before proceeding to full-text screening, thereby improving the accuracy and reliability of the final results. This resulted in 492 records (see Fig. 1).

B.3. Iterative study coding

Due to the large number of records and the fact that screening was primarily conducted by one person, an intermediate step was applied to reduce the number of records. This entailed a rough scan of complete records and removing incorrectly included articles. 190 articles were excluded as they very clearly did not investigate preferences, did not address nature-based solutions, reported only qualitative data or descriptive statistics, conducted simulations, or showed a clear absence of natural hazards. 11 articles were excluded because the records could not be retrieved. This reduced the body of records to 291 articles, allowing for more systematic consideration. These 291 records were partially recorded in Excel, taking note of the NbS investigated, the hazards, explanatory variables investigated, whether a monetary value for preferences was elicited (e.g., WTP), what methods were used to collect and analyse the data, and whether a theory was explicitly applied. Only the most frequently reported sociodemographic variables (income, age, gender, education, and distance) were coded to assess their significance for WTP. While this was done to limit the scope of the review, it does limit the provision of a complete account of explanatory variables. Any variables that could broadly be considered “social-psychological” (e.g., perceptions, experiences) were coded according to predefined categories based on existing reviews [10,15,199], and further adapted inductively during the coding process. It was furthermore decided only to consider studies using multivariate regression. After this broad round of coding, the studies were divided into two groups: those that used WTP as a dependent variable ($n = 162$) and those that did not ($n = 129$). Non-WTP studies were then separated from the main body of studies. However, non-WTP studies that met all other inclusion criteria ($n = 65$), except for the WTP value, were kept in a separate file to potentially enrich the discussion in the paper. Continuing with the 162 WTP studies only, a final round of in-depth coding was done. This included more detailed coding of independent variables, effects and significance. During this process, a final set of 72 WTP studies was excluded due to reasons that were previously overlooked during the screening process. All reasons for exclusion are reported in Fig. 1. Thus, 90 final records that met the inclusion criteria were selected for the review.

Once database coding was concluded, the category labels of social-psychological explanatory variables were revised based on common theories within the adaptation [35,200] and stated preference research field [49,201,202]. The categories are closely related to the Theory of Planned Behaviour and Protection-Motivation Theory. They are expanded by relevant additional categories frequently found in past research (see Table 1). The original labels used within the individual studies can be found in the supplementary database. In coding theory use, we considered only theories that address and inform the explanatory determinants of preferences, such as behavioural and psychological theories. In turn, theories that inform model construction or experimental setup were not noted as they were not the focus of this review. The classification of NbS, hazards, as well as the categorisation of social-psychological variables, relied on the operational definitions of constructs that are inconsistently labelled and measured across the literature, which may have introduced some subjectivity to determining study eligibility and variable classification. Furthermore, while aimed at making informed decisions on label classifications, our review combines classifications from various past reviews, making cross-review comparisons more challenging. Variation in the geographic, cultural, and hazard contexts across studies further contributes to the limitation of the generalisability of findings.

Appendix C. Crosstabulation of value elicitation method and economic model

Aligning with best practices in accounting for unobserved preference heterogeneity [203,204], most studies employed mixed parameter

Table C.1
Value Elicitation Method and Econometric Model used.

Category	DCE	CV	Total
Only Structural Heterogeneity			
<i>Subtotal</i>	10	37	47
Structural and Unobserved Heterogeneity			
Mixed/Random Parameter Logit	26	0	26
Latent Class Analysis	13	0	13
Generalised Multinomial Logit Model	1	0	1
Hybrid Latent Class	1	0	1
Random Effects Regression	0	1	1
Generalised Linear Mixed Model	0	1	1
Mixed Logit + Post Estimation	1	0	1
<i>Subtotal</i>	42	2	44
Total	52	39	91

Note: One study using CV and DCE accounts for a total of 91, as they were counted separately.

logit models (28%; also random parameter logit) or latent class models (14%). Less than half of the studies modelled this unobserved heterogeneity in addition to the structural one, with DCE studies making up the majority of these (see Table C.1).

Appendix D. Variation in predictors of willingness to pay across nature-based solution types

Hereafter we briefly describe the observations on the effects of the socio-demographic and social–psychological variables across NbS types, which can be found in Sheet “Patterns across NBS” of the Supplementary Database. For ease of interpretation, NbS are grouped into urban NbS (green roofs and walls, trees, parks and green spaces, and urban retention measures) and non-urban NbS (afforestation and forest restoration, water body renaturalization, mangroves, wetlands, beach nourishment, generic mentions of NbS, and other interventions). The patterns discussed below should be interpreted with caution. The number of studies within individual NbS categories is often small, and many variables are examined only in a limited subset of NbS types. As a result, the observed patterns are indicative rather than robust, and should not be read as stable generalisations.

Among socio-demographic variables, age is one of the few predictors that shows a relatively consistent pattern, being more often negatively associated with willingness to pay across both urban and non-urban NbS. This tendency appears most clearly for urban retention measures, trees, parks and green spaces, and afforestation or forest restoration. Education is more often positively associated with WTP, particularly for trees, parks and green spaces, green roofs and walls, afforestation and forest restoration, and water body renaturalization, although findings for urban retention measures are more mixed. Income also appears more often positive for non-urban NbS than for urban NbS, with the clearest positive patterns found for water body renaturalization and mangrove interventions, whereas results for urban NbS are more variable. Gender is frequently insignificant across NbS types, with no clear pattern in the direction of significant effects. Distance is examined less often, but where it is included it tends to be negative in non-urban NbS and mixed in urban contexts.

Among social–psychological variables, environmental attitude is most often positively associated with WTP, especially for urban retention measures. Knowledge and experience also tend to show positive associations, but the pattern varies considerably by NbS type: the clearest positive tendency is found in mangrove studies, whereas urban retention measures are characterised mainly by insignificant results. Risk perception of the hazard addressed stands out as the most consistently positive predictor for water body renaturalization, but for other NbS types the evidence is either mixed or too sparse to support any clear interpretation.

Other social–psychological variables are tested too infrequently and across too narrow a range of NbS types to allow broader conclusions. Overall, the available evidence suggests some tentative differences between NbS categories.

Appendix E. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nbsj.2026.100331>.

Data availability

Database of reviewed articles is attached as supplementary material.

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